

The Profound Influence of Social Entrepreneurship on the Advancement of Sustainable Development: A Systematic Review

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10706666>

Published Date: 26-February-2024

Abstract: Social entrepreneurship is a powerful tool for sustainable growth and solving societal issues. This study examined the profound influence of social entrepreneurship on the advancement of Sustainable development. The paper reviewed social entrepreneurs' significant impact on sustainable development. Searches included Scopus, PubMed, and Google Scholar. A Scopus Indexed Journal search found 10,147 peer-reviewed studies. Analysis was divided into two sections focused on the systematic review papers and key findings. The study used 2013-2022 Scopus Indexed Journal bibliometric and statistical data. Results show that social entrepreneurs promote sustainable development by solving social issues, creating novel service delivery models, and boosting the economy. It recommends that practitioners, policymakers, and scholars encourage social entrepreneurship practice and sustainable development.

Keywords: Social Entrepreneurship, Sustainable development, Sustainability, Innovation, Enterprise.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, there has been a growing recognition of the power of social entrepreneurship in addressing social issues and promoting sustainable development. According to Adams & Quagraine (2018), social entrepreneurship has recently become a potent strategy for addressing societal problems and fostering sustainable economic development. Moreover, Onileowo et al. (2021) posit that social entrepreneurs are persons or organisations that use entrepreneurial principles to develop innovative solutions to social problems to produce social value. Individuals are motivated by a vision for society and can find approaches to resolving and mitigating social issues in the areas where they are situated. Social entrepreneurship goes beyond conventional business models, emphasising societal effect more than financial gain. According to Raman et al. (2022), these enterprises generate social value through innovation and produce something new to mobilise resources to solve social problems efficiently. Also, they become change agents, adopting entrepreneurial strategies to offer systemic solutions to social and environmental issues (Quaye & Mensah, 2019). Social entrepreneurship can propel sustainable development, which is the primary reason for its significance. According to Radovič-Markovič and Živanovič (2019), social entrepreneurs contribute to realising the Sustainable Development Goals by working to solve social problems and encouraging the production of new forms of social value. The innovative approach and solution have the potential to bring about beneficial social transformation, economic expansion, and environmental preservation (Yıldız et al., 2014).

Both social entrepreneurship and sustainable development primarily emphasise improving the overall quality of life by bringing together environmental and social impact considerations (Uduji et al., 2021). Innovation and the discovery of new opportunities that arise in the market are two of the primary ways social entrepreneurs can bring about sustainable change.

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Several studies (Bansal et al., 2019; Johnson & Schaltegger, 2020; Dhahri et al., 2021; Kamaludin et al., 2021; Ahmad & Bajwa, 2023) have demonstrated the overall impact of impact of Social entrepreneurship. However, none of these studies have been extensively evaluated on sustainable development (Urmanaviciene & Arachchi, 2020; Duncan-Horner et al., 2022). Hence, the need to gain a deeper understanding of the sustainable impacts of social entrepreneurship on sustainable development and the various factors that play a role in determining their success or failure. Kamaludin et al., (2021) argued that these factors should be improved to determine the influence of social entrepreneurship, and by addressing these issues, a better understanding of social entrepreneurship and its influence on sustainable development can be achieved. Moreover, the influence of social entrepreneur's advantages in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals by focusing on improving society's most pressing problems and encouraging the production of new forms of social value are yet to be fully exploited, thus a need for further studies. Their innovative strategies and solutions have the potential to bring about beneficial social transformation, economic expansion, and environmental sustainability. Therefore, this paper provides insights into the existing social entrepreneurship research and systematically reviews social entrepreneurs' significant impact on advancing sustainable development. The study improves the overall understanding of social entrepreneurship by analysing its distinguishing characteristics, influence, and potential for promoting sustainable development. The results of this study will offer valuable insights for researchers, practitioners, and policymakers involved in the domain of social entrepreneurship, which can be applied to their respective endeavours.

However, despite the increased interest in social entrepreneurship, there is still a lack of clarity and agreement on the concept and definition of social entrepreneurship (Onwuka et al., 2015). Social entrepreneurship is a dynamic field where individuals strive to address social issues through innovative solutions, all while incorporating business practices. Further, passionate changemakers are driven by a deep commitment to creating a positive societal impact that fosters sustainable growth and constructive social change (Halkias et al., 2011). In contrast to conventional business strategies, social entrepreneurs are more concerned with making a positive social impact than making a profit. Thus, social entrepreneurs pool their resources to solve social issues and create value through creative innovations. Santos et al. (2022) opines that "social entrepreneurship" means using entrepreneurial ideas to resolve social problems. Entrepreneurship focusing on social good, or "social entrepreneurship," uses commercial methods to address societal issues. The goal of social entrepreneurs is to improve society as a whole through applying business principles to solve social problems (Hamdan et al., 2020). Moreover, social entrepreneurship is a growing movement that goes hand in hand with other popular trends like Socially Responsible Investment (SRI) and Environmental, Social, and Governance investing (ESG investing) (Landström, 2020).

According to Mazhar et al. (2022), social entrepreneurs contribute to accomplishing Sustainable Development Goals by solving social problems and fostering the production of new forms of social value. Strategic and innovative thinking can positively change society, economic growth, and environmental sustainability. However, social entrepreneurship's recent difficulty stems from its taking several forms. Entrepreneurs who focus on solving social issues are known as social entrepreneurs, as they use their business acumen to generate positive social impact and their business expertise to impact society positively. Along with socially responsible investment (SRI) and environmental, social, and governance investing (ESG investing), social entrepreneurship is a trend that is gaining popularity. Onileowo et al. (2022) opined that business people go beyond typical business models by placing a higher value on social impact than financial gain and organising resources to address social problems successfully. Innovating new approaches to social issues helps bring about positive change and build sustainable communities. Therefore, businesses that fit the definition of social entrepreneurship use traditional business metrics like profit, revenue, and stock price growth to evaluate their success. However, their primary goal is to maximise gains in social happiness rather than financial profit.

According to Amornkitvikai et al. (2022), Social entrepreneurs, who work to improve society by implementing new ideas and making better use of existing resources, create their ideas by first gaining knowledge of the connections between social problems and culture by playing a significant role in overcoming societal obstacles and enhancing the quality of life for underprivileged communities and individuals. The idea of social entrepreneurship is still in its infancy. As such, studies are still working to compile an inventory of the existing literature and pinpoint potential new lines of inquiry. As a means of promoting sustainable development and narrowing the gap between different socioeconomic groups, social entrepreneurship has emerged as gaining increasing importance; along with socially responsible investment (SRI) and environmental, social, and governance (ESG) investing, social entrepreneurship in a concept that is becoming increasingly popular (Kasri & Adilah Ismail, 2022). The idea of social entrepreneurship has recently come to be recognised as an essential aspect that plays a role in the improvement of public welfare and prosperity. Social entrepreneurs develop original

approaches to resolving social issues, putting the impact on society ahead of financial gain, and play an essential role in addressing societal difficulties and empowering disadvantaged groups and individuals, both of which they make significant contributions (Mars, 2022). Social entrepreneurship's impact in solving societal issues to ensure and contribute to economic development generally cannot be undermined. Hence, this study examines the profound influence of Social entrepreneurship on the advancement of Sustainable development and also contributes to the existing body of knowledge in the field of Social entrepreneurship and Sustainable development by enhancing the understanding of Social entrepreneurship and Sustainable development, pinpointing crucial factors that influence this relationship, offer valuable insights for researchers, practitioners, and policymakers and put forth frameworks for future studies.

2. SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP THEORY

Social entrepreneurship theory involves prioritising the interests of others above personal gain and actively pursuing sustainable solutions to problems that have been disregarded despite their potential positive impact. According to Steiner et al. (2022), social entrepreneurship involves efficiently allocating existing resources to create valuable outcomes for the community. In addition, it addresses the excellent impact on society ignored by individuals and government entities driven by self-interest. It mainly applies to positive externalities concentrated in specific areas and benefits marginalised segments of society. Social entrepreneurship is distinct from philanthropy, corporate social responsibility, and traditional entrepreneurship. The theoretical framework offers a clear structure to enhance academic research, educational efforts, and innovation strategies in social entrepreneurship. Social entrepreneurship has gained significant attention as a powerful tool for promoting sustainable development and addressing pressing social and environmental concerns (Samara and Samara, 2022).

The Social Entrepreneurship Theory, therefore, provides a framework that can be used to understand the role of social entrepreneurship in promoting sustainable development. The theory highlights the significance of developing sustainable solutions to address social and environmental concerns, which is crucial in tackling the current challenges faced by society. Fernández and Bentley (2022) suggested that social entrepreneurship can substantially impact accelerating sustainable development. According to Foroozanfar (2022), social entrepreneurship and sustainable development reveal that social entrepreneurs play a crucial role in addressing social issues, introducing creative approaches to service delivery, and promoting economic growth. In contrast, Pratiwi et al. (2022) posit that social entrepreneurs play a crucial role in advancing Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by addressing current social issues and promoting the development of innovative forms of social impact and that these positive societal transformations contribute to economic growth and environmental sustainability. Consequently, Conway et al. (2016) explore the various dimensions of the influence that social entrepreneurship has on sustainable development. The findings highlighted potential outcomes of social entrepreneurship, including creating new jobs, expanding the economy, and formulating innovative approaches to delivering services. In addition, social entrepreneurship has the potential to address significant societal and environmental challenges, including poverty, inequality, and climate change. Therefore, Social Entrepreneurship Theory applies to examining sustainable development as it highlights the importance of innovation in addressing social, economic, and environmental challenges (Kamaludin, 2023) and as pinpointed, it is crucial to address social and environmental problems by employing innovative techniques to encourage sustainable development and highlights the importance of solving these issues. It highlights the importance of creating environmentally and socially responsible solutions to current challenges, which is crucial in addressing society's problems.

Ultimately, the Theory of Social Entrepreneurship provides a framework that can be used to understand the impact of social entrepreneurship on promoting sustainable development. Studies (Ponto et al., 2015; Zhan & Gu, 2022; Zhen et al., 2022) have shown that social entrepreneurship is crucial in advancing sustainable development. It offers practical solutions to social issues, creates innovative service delivery models, boosts the economy and emphasises the importance of social impact; entrepreneurship can foster meaningful transformations in society while enhancing economic growth and environmental sustainability. Therefore, policymakers, practitioners, and academics must promote the practice of social entrepreneurship and sustainable development to create meaningful social impact and tackle the challenges currently confronting society.

2.1 Social Entrepreneurship and Sustainable Development

The heightened emphasis on the sustainable development goal has been propelled by mounting apprehension around environmental issues. The primary purpose of social entrepreneurship, and entrepreneurship in general, is intricately linked

to the endeavours pursued by entrepreneurs. These efforts encompass the creation of novel products, the investigation of untapped markets, and the implementation of groundbreaking concepts. To effectively design strategies that promote sustainable development through entrepreneurship, it is essential to identify the characteristics that impact both forms of entrepreneurship (Afolabi & Oye, 2015). Academic interest in sustainable development has been growing since the 1990s, as evidenced by the emergence of relevant literature. According to Ponto et al. (2015), sustainable development is characterised by a long-term balance that avoids harm to others and resource depletion. Nevertheless, sustainable development in social entrepreneurship involves creating long-lasting solutions for social or environmental issues currently overlooked by the market. Micah & Omolayo (2022) opined that the exploration of sustainable development in social entrepreneurship has captured the attention of scholars worldwide and is considered a crucial aspect of the growth of the social entrepreneurship sector. Mdjalose (2022) argued that sustainable development is centred around preserving the diverse social connections within flourishing communities. Furthermore, sustainable development strives to create physical, cultural, and social environments that enhance well-being and cultivate a sense of community among the people living in those regions. The macro-level emphasises the importance of individuals' physical well-being and meeting their basic needs, such as housing, food, and clothing.

Meanwhile, according to Javed et al. (2019), numerous factors contribute to a well-rounded and inclusive society on a smaller scale. These factors encompass various aspects of a well-rounded and inclusive community. They involve elements such as the general well-being of individuals, equality, the integration of different social and cultural groups, the presence of diversity, a close-knit community, open and effective communication, active involvement in community affairs, access to necessary social facilities, and a feeling of safety and security. Alonso Dos Santos et al. (2022) highlighted the significance of considering both the process and outcome of sustainable development within a social infrastructure system. Study findings revealed sustainable approaches and products within the social entrepreneurship ecosystem, focusing on sustainable development. Conducting a preliminary study to understand sustainable development better is essential. It could be accomplished by utilising a foundational conceptual framework developed by Kamaludin et al. (2021), as shown in Figure 1, establishing a link between social entrepreneurship and sustainability. The conceptual direction revealed that the social dimension includes five variables: social mission, value creation, networks, community, and change. Furthermore, this study delves into the social business processes and measurement of the social impact of social enterprises to gain valuable insights into their influence on sustainable development.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework for Social Entrepreneurship and Sustainable Development (Kamaludin et al., 2021)

2.2 Social Enterprise and Sustainable Development

Sustainable social enterprises are a potent tool for addressing societal issues and creating positive change by providing goods and services. These businesses are driven by a desire to impact society while generating a profit positively, innovate dramatically and contribute to creating a more sustainable future (Adams & Quagraine, 2018). Entrepreneurs are frequently recognised as the foremost catalysts of sustainable development. There has been limited scholarly discussion regarding the anticipated course of this process despite the recognition of entrepreneurs as potential agents for addressing unmet social needs. Consequently, the innovative social entrepreneurship approach entered academic journals and executive organisations' operations (González-Serrano et al., 2020). Social entrepreneurship gained popularity throughout the 1970s as a viable and sustainable approach to addressing societal challenges. Examining the evolution of social entrepreneurship definitions has provided significant insights into the problem-solving dynamics associated with social enterprise. The measure of a social enterprise's success is contingent upon its allocation of capital and the magnitude of economic benefits it bestows upon individuals and communities rather than being purely reliant on its profitability rate. According to Jamali & Lund-Thomsen (2017), the core aim of social entrepreneurship is to generate sustainable positive impacts in the broader society, exceeding its initial intention. Social entrepreneurship is crucial to accomplish societal goals and efficiently administer an organisation. The field of social entrepreneurship is centred on the cultivation of innovative strategies to facilitate effective and profitable societal transformation.

Entrepreneurs operating in the social sector are individuals responsible for managing resources to achieve social objectives. Social entrepreneurship's primary aim is not just to create financial rewards for its benefactors. Instead, it focuses on improving the overall welfare of diverse groups and having a substantial and beneficial influence on the development of the individuals it caters to. According to (Bansal et al., 2019), social entrepreneurs seek to achieve financial gains by facilitating sustainable social transformation. Individuals in this profession commonly possess the necessary qualifications and exhibit preferences that cater to the needs of individuals, organisations, and entire areas. Entrepreneurs participate in traditional and social entrepreneurship endeavours to generate profits from several avenues. Nevertheless, the fundamental differences between these two kinds are rooted in entrepreneurial self-discovery, commonly known as "discovery." Promoting social values in cultures that face challenges can facilitate the recovery process, resulting in the emergence of innovative employment opportunities.

Despite the growing body of literature on the subject, there are still many unanswered questions in social entrepreneurship (Alonso Dos Santos et al., 2022). Therefore, further investigation is needed to understand the long-term effects of social entrepreneurship initiatives on sustainable development and the factors that contribute to their success or failure. However, addressing these issues is crucial for further developing social entrepreneurship and maximising its potential for long-term prosperity while minimising social inequities. Having a shared language and framework is essential for researchers, policymakers, and practitioners to effectively collaborate in promoting social entrepreneurship and its impact on sustainable development, as the existing literature lacks a unified theoretical framework for analysing the factors influencing social entrepreneurship and its implications for sustainable development, (Zhan & Gu, 2022). Social entrepreneurship is closely intertwined with the pursuit of sustainable development. This study is based on a comprehensive examination and analysis of academic journals, conference proceedings, lecture notes, and proceedings from symposia and workshops to explore the extensive and diverse social entrepreneurship and sustainable development field. Yu and Zhu (2022) assert that social entrepreneurs play a crucial role in facilitating sustainable advancement through their efforts to address social challenges, innovate service delivery models, and contribute to economic growth. According to Shiri et al. (2022), various factors, including social persuasion, social networking, role models, peer norms, self-efficacy, social support, empathy, moral judgment, education, religion, caste, familial background, and socioeconomic background, have been identified as influencing social entrepreneurship. In 2022, Alanzi et al. Opined that the elements of social entrepreneurship could vary depending on the environment and culture in which it is practised. However, Upadhyay, Upadhyay, and Dwivedi (2022) argued that social entrepreneurship performance's most significant factors include individual characteristics, organisational variables, and organisational resource factors. Social entrepreneurs must possess solid relationship-building skills and actively engage with their communities to drive meaningful change. Collaboration with different organisations, stakeholders, and individuals is necessary to achieve our shared goals. The approach also prioritises the opinions and participation of those most affected by the issue.

International Journal of Novel Research in Marketing Management and Economics

 Vol. 11, Issue 1, pp: (83-103), Month: January - April 2024, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

Madjdi and Zolfaghari (2022) posit that the ultimate goal of social entrepreneurship is to positively impact the world by seeking to improve it. Ways to accomplish this include improving the lives of underserved populations, protecting the environment, promoting social justice and human rights, and promoting social equality. Social entrepreneurs assess their success based on financial gain and their businesses' positive effects on society and the environment. Moreover, Addae Ellenwood (2022) agreed that social entrepreneurs are creating impactful and sustainable solutions to address societal and environmental challenges, leading to positive change in the world. Social entrepreneurship is widely recognised as a highly regarded approach that empowers individuals to generate a positive and beneficial impact on society. Molina & Pérez-Garrido (2022) asserted that success in social entrepreneurship relies on the harmonious amalgamation of business operations with a virtuous social objective. According to Zhen, Jin, and Hongchen (2022), social entrepreneurship is cultivating an environment that promotes innovation, establishing strategic partnerships, engaging and collaborating with communities, and ultimately developing sustainable and practical solutions to tackle urgent social and environmental challenges. Understanding the fundamental concepts and components that drive social entrepreneurship is crucial for supporting and promoting the growth of essential fields and their positive impact on the global economy. However, Onileowo et al. (2022) opined that there are considerable barriers to entry for social entrepreneurs seeking funding for business creation and expansion. A lack of funding is one of the biggest problems facing social entrepreneurs and those working towards sustainable development, as supported by (Can, 2022; and Jia 2022 Khalid et al., 2022), in the regulatory setting is a significant factor in whether or not social entrepreneurship and sustainable development can flourish. Incentives and assistance for social entrepreneurs in a conducive regulatory environment can positively impact sustainable development. Social capital is the fourth category of capital, encompassing networks, connections, and trust that enable effective collaboration among individuals and businesses. It is crucial in facilitating access to resources, information, and support, promoting social entrepreneurship and sustainable development. As the fifth essential element, innovation is vital for promoting social entrepreneurship and long-term growth. Entrepreneurs dedicated to societal well-being employ innovative strategies to address social challenges and enhance the collective welfare. Table 1, therefore, depicts scholarly reviews on social entrepreneurship's significance in advancing sustainable development

Table 1: Social Entrepreneurship Brief Review and Insights

S/N	Title/Author/Year	Insights	Methods Used	Conclusion
1	Social Entrepreneurship as a Path for Social Change and Driver of Sustainable Development: A Systematic Review and Research Agenda, (Bansal et al., 2019).	This paper systematically reviews existing literature on social entrepreneurship's role in social change and sustainable development and sets an agenda for future research.	-Inspired by Tranfield, Denyer, and Smart. Used Web of Science database for search	- Need to increase focus on developing countries. More empirical studies are needed to understand the outcomes
2	Entrepreneurship for Sustainable Development: A Review and Multilevel Causal Mechanism Framework (Johnson & Schaltegger, 2020).	Sustainable entrepreneurship is a multilevel phenomenon that connects social, environmental, and economic dimensions in entrepreneurial processes and market transformations.	N/A	- Multilevel causal mechanism framework for entrepreneurship and sustainable development. Connection between social, environmental, and economic dimensions.
3	Influence of Social, Environmental and Economic Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) over Continuation of Entrepreneurship and Competitiveness (Del-Aguila-Arcentaes et al., 2022).	The study found that social Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) positively influence economic SDGs, contributing to the continuation of entrepreneurship and competitiveness.	PLS-SEM technique used for analysis.	Social and environmental SDGs positively influence economic SDGs. - Economic SDGs positively influence entrepreneurship and competitiveness.
4	Behavioral entrepreneurship for achieving sustainable development goals (Dhahri et al., 2021).	Opportunity-driven entrepreneurship positively impacts sustainable	-Long-run estimates. Short and Long-run causality analyses	Opportunity entrepreneurship has a positive impact on sustainable development.

		development's economic, social, and environmental dimensions, while necessity-driven entrepreneurship hurts environmental sustainability.		Necessity entrepreneurship hurts ecological sustainability.
5	Understanding the social entrepreneur: a new intentions model for advancing equity, social justice and sustainability (Duncan-Horner et al., 2022).	Social entrepreneurship has the potential to significantly impact sustainable development by addressing social and environmental challenges through innovative approaches.	Qualitative research with multiple case designs. Interviews, data analysis, and fieldwork observations.	The paper presents a new intentions model for social entrepreneurship. The model outlines The phases of enterprise development and critical enabling factors.
6	The Effective Methods and Practices for Accelerating Social Entrepreneurship Through Corporate Social Responsibility (Urmanaviciene & Arachchi, 2020).	Social entrepreneurship and corporate social responsibility aim to balance profitability and social impact by creating innovative solutions to social issues while maintaining socially responsible business conduct.	-Qualitative inductive research methodology. Content analysis method	CSR activities can accelerate social entrepreneurship development. Supporting social entrepreneurs through CSR creates social value
7	El desarrollo sostenible a través de empresas sociales en comunidades indígenas de América Latina (Vázquez-Maguirre, 2019).	Social enterprises contribute to territorial development by creating employment opportunities, promoting local value chains, and addressing social and environmental issues.	Qualitative case study research method- collecting data through interviews, observation, and document analysis	Indigenous social enterprises promote local development through employment, new businesses, environmental awareness, infrastructure, and local product markets—entrepreneurial ecosystem and social innovation support Indigenous communities through social enterprises.
8	Development of the sustainable entrepreneurship model Fatemeh,"non-dropping-particle":"","parse-names":false,"suffix":"","dropping-particle":"","family":"Tooranloo","given":"Hossein Sayyadi","non-dropping-particle":"","parse-names":false,"suffix":"","container-title":"Malaysian Management Journal","id":"ITEM-1","issue":"July","issued":{"date-parts":["2020"]},"page":"103-143","title":"Development of the Sustainable Entrepreneurship Model","type":"article-journal","volume":"24","uris":["http://www.mendeley.com/documents/?uuiid=c6cd3fcf-60a5-4159-97df-bab217600a2f"]},"mendeley":{"formattedCitation":"(Kazemi et al., 2020)","plainTextFormattedCitation":"(Kazemi et al., 2020)","previouslyFormattedCitation":	Information should be given about industrial clusters in Nigeria and South Africa and their relation to sustainable entrepreneurship.	Interpretive Structural Modeling (ISM) approach	The research has theoretical and practical implications.

	on": "(Kazemi et al., 2020)", "properties": {"noteIndex": 0}, "schema": "https://github.com/citation-style-language/schema/raw/master/csl-citation.json"} (Kazemi et al., 2020)			
9	Paths out of poverty: Social entrepreneurship and sustainable development (Zhang et al., 2022)	Social entrepreneurship has become a new sustainable development path to solve rural poverty and offers ideas for sustainable development in rural areas.	- case study method Analysis of the social entrepreneurship process	- Social entrepreneurship is a sustainable path to rural poverty reduction. Enterprises integrate farmers into their value chain for poverty alleviation.
10	Social Entrepreneurship as a Tool of Sustainable Development (Břanda & Urbančiková, 2020)	The article needs to explain the key differences between social and sustainable entrepreneurship.	Survey of Slovak social entrepreneurs. - Likert scale in questionnaire.	- Social entrepreneurship is still in development in Slovakia. Social entrepreneurs prioritise solving social problems
11	Social entrepreneurship: Environmental sustainability (Fhiri et al., 2021)	The paper discusses the role of social entrepreneurship in addressing environmental problems and proposes a conceptual framework for social entrepreneurship initiatives.		- Proposes a conceptual framework for social entrepreneurship initiatives. Formulates a tentative framework for environmental sustainability aspects of social entrepreneurship
12	Social Entrepreneurship: A Bibliometric-Based Research Trend. (Aliya Yesmin, 2021)	Social entrepreneurship is a popular area of research and practice that addresses social issues and promotes sustainable development.	-Bibliometric statistics. - Graphical visualisation	- Social entrepreneurship is widespread in research and practice. The article analyses annual publications, top authors, organisations, nations, and publishers in the field.
13	Social Entrepreneurship and Sustainability: A Conceptual Framework. (Kamaludin et al., 2021)	The paper discusses the link between social entrepreneurship and sustainability but does not explicitly address the role of social entrepreneurship in promoting sustainable business practices in UK SMEs		- Linking social entrepreneurship to sustainability is essential. - There is growing interest in this research field.
14	Social entrepreneurship and corporate sustainable development. Evidence from Vietnam. (Hoang Tien et al., 2020)	The chapter discusses the relationship between social entrepreneurship and sustainability, highlighting social entrepreneurship's importance in advancing sustainable development.	N/A	Social entrepreneurship is a valuable tool for social sustainability. Effective implementation of social sustainability depends on social entrepreneurship.
15	The role of social entrepreneurship in socioeconomic development: a meta-analysis of the nascent field. (Ahmad & Bajwa, 2023).	The trends observed from scientific literature reviews on social enterprise and social entrepreneurship include consistent research growth, influential articles and journals, and specific research directions.	Bibliometric-content meta-analysis. Software use: Histcite, VOSviewer, Biblioshiny	Increase in research publications on social entrepreneurship and socioeconomic development. It identifies trends, research streams, and future research directions.

2.3 Entrepreneurship Determinant Factors for Sustainable Development

2.3.1 Sociocultural Factors

Sociocultural factors have a substantial impact on promoting entrepreneurial activity from two perspectives. Without robust institutions safeguarding property rights, only a few economic players would engage in entrepreneurship. If the rules for this activity are unclear or cause delays in decision-making owing to bureaucracy, it may negatively impact entrepreneurial activity. Institutions are responsible for establishing the operating rules to ensure smooth operation. Several studies (Krammer, 2017; Pandov et al., 2019), indicate that the institutional framework affects social entrepreneurship. Some (Baumol, 2023; Hall et al., 2010) argue it might hinder it. According to Nikolakis et al. (2022), there are two primary institution categories: formal and informal. Formal institutions are characterised by a significant cultural element that serves as a driving force for entrepreneurs. Studies by (Jiang et al. (2022); Omri (2020); Pandov et al. (2019) posits that the rules established by these institutions are intended to enhance economic liberty and minimise corruption, hence fostering a favourable environment for entrepreneurship. Meanwhile, education and skill development are essential for entrepreneurs, as higher levels of education promote innovation and effective utilisation of resources, enabling them to recognise market opportunities as schooling can be seen as a representative measure of education and human capital (Qi et al., 2022).

2.3.2 Economic Factors

Several factors, such as general and social variables, can impact entrepreneurial activity within this sector. The government's fiscal policy is instrumental in driving entrepreneurship. Government intervention plays a crucial role in boosting entrepreneurship by tackling market failures caused by unexpected events or inefficient allocation of resources (Audretsch & Link, 2019). Government spending policies can play a crucial role in fostering entrepreneurship. Government creates an environment that encourages entrepreneurial endeavours by focusing on income distribution, investing in education, and prioritising research and development (Su, 2022).

Meanwhile, investing in education is an essential factor that contributes to the overall development of society. It allows businesses to improve their efficiency and effectively identify market opportunities. According to Méndez-Picazo et al. (2021), establishing a fair income distribution is crucial to creating a harmonious social atmosphere that encourages economic activity and fuels entrepreneurship. Government policies can indirectly support entrepreneurship by implementing employment policies. Increasing employment levels boost market demand, leading to increased production and the introduction of innovative products. It can significantly improve the efficiency of development efforts and create new market opportunities, thereby encouraging the rise of aspiring entrepreneurs. There is an expected positive association between employment and social entrepreneurship. Some argue that government measures could potentially support unproductive enterprises, which could hinder economic growth (Al-Faryan & Shil, 2022). Other significant economic factors include capital expenditure and research and development. Entrepreneurs can significantly improve their competitiveness by integrating environmentally sustainable technologies. It can inspire other entrepreneurs to embrace similar practices (Pandov et al., 2019). Both attributes have a positive impact on both general and social entrepreneurship. The sociocultural factors include corruption, economic freedom, education, and human capital, while economic considerations include income distribution, job opportunities, investments in fixed assets, and research and development expenses. In the grand scheme, both types of entrepreneurships contribute positively to advancing sustainable development.

3. THEMATIC ANALYSIS OF SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

The analysis comprised two main stages: conducting an extensive literature review and bibliometric research exploring the extant scholarly literature about the nexus of social entrepreneurship and sustainable development. The study included various sources, comprising academic publications, conference proceedings, lecture notes, symposia, and workshop proceedings. A thematic content analysis approach was employed to improve the understanding of previous works about social entrepreneurship and sustainable development. This study examines the various factors influencing social entrepreneurship and its effect on advancing sustainable development. Statistical approaches are employed to evaluate articles with keywords relevant to the research topic. The study examines the journals included in the Scopus Indexed online database as an extensive repository of academic material spanning various disciplines to identify emerging trends and determine the characteristics of these publications in the relevant subject. The study review aligns with a methodology commonly employed in conventional research. Results and findings are presented and thoroughly examined.

4. RESULTS PRESENTATION AND DISCUSSION

As presented in Figures 1, 2, and 3, the research articles examined in this study provide information on subject areas, publication years, and countries of origin, respectively. The study findings indicate that social entrepreneurship is crucial in promoting sustainable development through its contributions to solving social problems, establishing new firms and service delivery models, and stimulating economic growth. Findings revealed that social capital, innovation, financing, and the regulatory environment exerted significant influence on social entrepreneurship and its contribution to the promotion of sustainable development.

Documents by subject area

Figure 2a

Documents per year by source

Figure 2b

Figure 2: Percentage of Publications by Subject Area and documents per year by source relative to Social Entrepreneurship and Sustainable Development

Figure 2a depicts business management harbouring social entrepreneurship at 24.1% volume of publications on social entrepreneurship and sustainable development from a search analysis conducted on Scopus index journals published from the year 2014 to 2022, being the largest in the field of publication as followed by Social Sciences (22.4%), Environmental Sciences (13.7%), Energy (10.2%), Economics (7%), Engineering (6.8%) Computer (6.2%), Decision Science (3.2%), Psychology (2.2%), Arts and humanity (1.5%) and others as (2.6%). Further, social entrepreneurship and sustainable development publications have an increasing trend in the year under review (2013-2022), as shown in Figure 2b. In the year 2022, records over 590 publications from reputable journals of sustainability Switzerland. However, the Journal of Cleaner Energy, Technological Forecasting and Social Change, Business Strategy and the Environment and Business Research Journal publications published less than 180 volumes from 2013 to 2022, signifying a consistent rise in the Journal of Sustainability Switzerland of Social Entrepreneurship and Sustainable Development.

The study findings clearly show the significant role played by social entrepreneurship in promoting sustainable development accomplished by its capacity to facilitate the resolution of social issues, build innovative institutions and models for service delivery, and encourage economic growth. These findings are supported by the works cited in references 1, 2, and 4. Several factors were identified as significant in determining the influence of social entrepreneurship on sustainable development. These factors comprise access to financial resources, the regulatory environment, social capital, and innovation (Ato, 2023; Wen, 2032). These findings provide valuable insights to policymakers, practitioners, and researchers, improving their understanding of effective policies for promoting social entrepreneurship and sustainable development. Social entrepreneurship is widely recognised as a potent catalyst for achieving positive social change and tackling various societal concerns. The idea entails the development of innovative and sustainable business models that prioritise social and environmental benefits alongside financial profitability. With the ultimate goal of promoting sustainable development, social entrepreneurship researchers employ their findings to strengthen their networks and relationships. A search was conducted on countries with regional territories using the Scopus index journals to facilitate this procedure. The

investigation was limited to a few countries, namely the United Kingdom, with the highest number of publications at over 2,400, followed by the United States with 2,300 publications. Other countries included in the search were China, Italy with 1,377 publications, Australia, Spain with 1,455 publications, Germany, Malaysia, South Africa, and the Netherlands, which had the lowest number of publications at 285. These publications were sourced and analysed, dealing with comparable subject matters, as depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Scopus Indexed Search; Documents by country or territory

Further, a comprehensive and systematic search from 2013 to 2022 was conducted on the profound influence of social entrepreneurship in advancing sustainable development, and results were analysed using indexed Scopus imploring bibliography analysis, as shown in Figure 4 and Figure 5, which depicts the green area from the overlay and density visualisation view.

Figure 4 & 5: The Green Area from Overlay and Density Visualisation View

This understanding was obtained through a bibliography analysis review of online Scopus index publications from around the world, as the US has provided a significant consideration and consultation process that aims to identify end-user needs, research gaps, and possible synergies, resulting in a valuable resource for advancing sustainability development of social entrepreneurship research focused on a variety. The results from Vos viewer analysis suggest that a significant amount of research has yet to be carried out, as shown by the search result of over 10,147 and analysed using Vos viewer Scopus

indexing on bibliography. The fact that only a little research has been done on this topic is shown by the overlay visualisation in Figures 4 and 5 of the Vos viewer Scopus indexing on bibliographies viewpoint in the context of social entrepreneurship in advancing sustainable development from published Scopus index journals. Figure 5 depicts the understanding of the volume of research conducted on the function and interactions of social entrepreneurship and the research findings' advancement in sustainability developmental goals. However, entrepreneurship research often needs to be more organised. Thus, a study on this topic and the presentation of a conceptual review are crucial (Mohamadi et al., 2014). Insights into the factors that influence social entrepreneurship and its role in achieving sustainable development are provided by this study. Access to financing, regulatory environment, social capital, and innovation were found to be significant determinants of social entrepreneurship's impact on sustainable development. Study findings indicate that social entrepreneurship is vital in promoting sustainable development by facilitating social problem-solving, establishing innovative organisations and service delivery models, and stimulating economic growth (Kim & Lim, 2017). Factors such as access to financing, the regulatory framework, social capital, and innovation were identified as influential in shaping the impact of social entrepreneurship on sustainable development (Di Vaio et al., 2022).

There is a strong correlation between the regulatory environment and the success of social entrepreneurs. The success of social entrepreneurs can be encouraged by creating a regulatory framework that provides incentives for and acknowledgement of social enterprise. It is the job of governments and policymakers to create an atmosphere that is favourable to success. They make suitable regulatory environments, provide financial incentives, and open doors to valuable resources and networks to accomplish this goal. Social capital the web of personal and professional connections within a community is essential for social entrepreneurs. Social entrepreneurship can be more effective and sustainable if it fosters partnerships with various constituencies. These include local communities, government agencies, non-profit organisations, and investors. When addressing complex socioeconomic issues, collaboration and alliances can prove indispensable. Conclusively, social entrepreneurship plays a crucial role in promoting sustainable development due to its emphasis on solving social problems, developing novel organisations and approaches to providing services and fostering economic growth. Access to funds, the regulatory climate, social capital, and innovation are all crucial factors determining how social entrepreneurship contributes to sustainable development. The results of this study provide essential information that can aid scholars, policymakers, and practitioners in pursuing sustainable development through social entrepreneurship.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS

The study examines the profound influence of social entrepreneurship on the advancement of sustainable development. Based on the research findings, it is evident that social entrepreneurs play a crucial role in promoting sustainable development through their efforts to tackle social issues, develop innovative service delivery models, and enhance the economy. Several key factors have been recognised as significant for social entrepreneurship and its contribution to sustainable development. These factors encompass access to financing, the regulatory environment, social capital, and innovation. Social entrepreneurs are those involved in creating innovative businesses or evolving existing ones to address societal needs. Social entrepreneurs play a crucial role in driving sustainable development through their efforts to address social issues, devise innovative approaches to service provision, and contribute to economic growth.

The study found various factors, such as the availability of financial resources, the regulatory framework, social connections, and innovative thinking, impact the role of social entrepreneurship in promoting sustainable development. The presence of social entrepreneurship significantly facilitates the advancement of sustainable development. Social entrepreneurs have a notable impact on tackling social issues and positively contributing to society and the environment. Individuals and groups develop new methods to address poverty, inequality, education, healthcare, and environmental sustainability. Through their diverse endeavours, individuals contribute to the enhancement of society and establish lucrative sources of income. Social entrepreneurship addresses societal challenges and plays a significant role in advancing innovative service delivery models.

Further, Social entrepreneurship is crucial in promoting economic growth and development. Social enterprises are vital for job creation, economic growth, and fostering innovation in local communities. They focus on engaging with marginalised communities, creating jobs, and promoting economic advancement in regions that traditional enterprise approaches have neglected. Entrepreneurial individuals actively contribute to the growth and enhancement of communities by applying entrepreneurial principles. The success and growth of social entrepreneurship initiatives heavily rely on the presence of

financial resources. Social entrepreneurs frequently require assistance securing funding from conventional channels because they primarily focus on generating social impact rather than solely prioritising financial gains. The significance of impact investments is increasingly acknowledged with the rise of funding options, such as social impact bonds and impact investment funds, designed to promote social entrepreneurship.

Policymakers play a vital role in creating an enabling environment for social entrepreneurs. It can be achieved through offering legal assistance, enacting financial incentives, and facilitating opportunities to develop meaningful relationships with resources and networks. Establishing a regulatory framework plays a pivotal role in promoting the advancement and effectiveness of social entrepreneurship, thereby making significant contributions towards attaining sustainable development goals. It is essential to create an enabling environment for social entrepreneurship, enact regulations and policies that recognise its significance and offer incentives for its growth and achievement. The active participation of governmental bodies and political figures plays a crucial role in attaining favourable outcomes through enacting laws, providing financial incentives, and facilitating the availability of resources and networks. Also, establishing robust connections with stakeholders, including local communities, government agencies, non-profit organisations, and investors, significantly improves the effectiveness and sustainability of social entrepreneurship efforts. Moreover, establishing collaborative connections and partnerships is pivotal in solving complex socioeconomic challenges. The significance and vitality of innovation in social entrepreneurship are widely recognised. Social entrepreneurs are crucial in challenging existing policies and practices by devising innovative and lasting solutions to address societal issues. The strategy employed by the individuals combines technology, design thinking approaches, and social innovation to create scalable solutions that provide substantial effects that require the creation of novel frameworks, methodologies, and strategies to facilitate significant transformation in the business sector. Social entrepreneurship acts as sustainable advancement by effectively tackling societal challenges, introducing innovative service models, and promoting economic growth. The evaluation of the influence of social entrepreneurship on sustainable development is contingent upon crucial factors such as access to financial resources, the legal framework, social capital, and innovation. This study offers valuable recommendations for policymakers, practitioners, and scholars to advance social entrepreneurship and sustainable development. The development of social entrepreneurship holds the potential to foster a future marked by heightened sustainability and equality for all individuals and the economy at large.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

Policymakers, practitioners, and scholars can use the study's recommendations to advance social entrepreneurship and sustainable development. Developing legal frameworks that facilitate the growth and sustainability of social enterprises is crucial in fostering sustainable economic development. Allocating financial resources and other assets enables social enterprise development and stimulates sustainable growth. Enhancing the community's social capital by promoting effective communication collaboration and cultivating trust among its members. Encouraging a sense of uniqueness by incentivising and assisting individuals who engage in social entrepreneurship. Study recommendations provide significant information for policymakers, practitioners, and scholars who are interested in advancing the fields of social entrepreneurship and sustainable development. Governments and policymakers can create regulatory frameworks that promote the development of social entrepreneurship and facilitate sustainable development. Achievement of this goal can be realised using the establishment of regulatory frameworks, offering of tax benefits, and the facilitation of access to crucial resources and networks. Implementing policies and regulations that effectively recognise and offer incentives for social entrepreneurship can create a favourable environment in which social entrepreneurs can thrive. It entails the creation of a legally robust structure for social enterprises, introducing financial incentives to stimulate impact investors, and streamlining regulatory processes related to social enterprises. The goal is to support the allocation of financial resources and various assets to promote the success of social enterprise and enable its sustainable growth. Procuring financial resources influences the success and growth of social entrepreneurship initiatives.

Policymakers can play a crucial role in creating an enabling environment for social entrepreneurs by offering financial assistance and other necessary resources that involve the creation of customised financial instruments, such as social impact bonds and impact investment funds, to support social entrepreneurship initiatives. Facilitate the growth of the community's social capital through fostering effective communication, productive collaboration, and the nurturing of trust. Social capital is a fundamental factor in promoting social entrepreneurship, encompassing a complex network of relationships, interpersonal ties, and interdependence within a specific community. Establishing solid and resilient relationships with

various stakeholders, including local communities, government bodies, non-profit groups, and investors, can enhance the effectiveness and sustainability of social entrepreneurship initiatives. Policymakers can promote the development of efficient communication channels, allow productive collaboration, and build trust among various societal actors by creating platforms that enable the engagement between social entrepreneurs and essential stakeholders. Moreover, lawmakers can actively promote establishing partnerships and collaborative initiatives while recognising the crucial significance of social capital in driving significant societal advancements. Promote innovation development by offering incentives and support to individuals engaged in social entrepreneurship. The effort to promote innovation is an inherent characteristic of social entrepreneurship. Policymakers have the potential to encourage innovation by appropriately recognising and providing incentives to social entrepreneurs who demonstrate the capability to design and execute innovative and sustainable solutions to societal challenges. It involves the creation of recognition and commendation programmes for individuals interested in social entrepreneurship, providing guidance and support, and promoting the importance of innovation in driving societal change. Social entrepreneurship can drive sustainable change by solving societal challenges, developing innovative systems for delivering vital services, and strengthening the economy. The study's suggestions offer significant information for policymakers, practitioners, and researchers seeking to improve the fields of social entrepreneurship and sustainable development through the development of regulatory frameworks that support the sustainability of social enterprise, promote sustainable development, and facilitate the allocation of funds and necessary resources to encourage social enterprise and sustained growth, improving the social capital of communities by promoting effective communication, collaboration, and trust, and promoting innovation by offering incentives and support to social entrepreneurs, cultivating a future marked by equity and sustainability, ultimately benefiting all individuals in society.

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